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Some Experiments in the Friedel-Craft Reaction with Methyl- β -Resorcyrate

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FRIEDEL-Craft butyrylation of methyl β -resorcyrate(I) has been reported¹ to yield methyl 2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyryl benzoate(II), m.p. 69°, and methyl 2,4-dihydroxy-5-butyryl benzoate(III), m.p. 90°, and the

We also studied the valerylation and caproylation of (I) under Friedel-Craft conditions. Equimolecular amounts of (I) and corresponding acid chlorides were heated with 3 moles of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ in nitrobenzene for 4 hours. In both the cases, the corresponding 3- and 5-acyl esters were obtained which were separated by fractional crystallisation from petroleum ether. The less soluble compound was the *-* isomer. The esters were colourless crystalline solids and were characterised by the formation of 2,4-DNP derivatives. The structures of the compounds were established by their alkaline hydrolysis to the corresponding benzoic acids crystallised from dil. EtOH, which were decarboxylated either by heating with 10% NaOH for 4 hours (in case of 3-acyl acids) or boiling with quinoline and copper powder (in case of 5-acyl acids) to the known acyl resorcinol derivatives²⁻⁵.

The Friedel-Craft reaction of I with *p*-toluoyl chloride also yielded the corresponding 3- and 5-substituted esters, separated by fractional crystallisation from alcohol. Hydrolysis of the esters with cold alkali (10% NaOH) afforded the corresponding toluoyl benzoic acids which were decarboxylated by boiling with alkali (4 hrs.) to known resorcinol derivatives⁶. The latter were also obtained directly from the esters by boiling with alkali under the above conditions (Table).

All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Acid chloride	Esters obtained/solvent	Yield	M.P.	2,4-DNP M.P.	M.P. of the benzoic acid
<i>n</i> -Valerylchloride	1) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-5-valeryl benzoate (EtOH)	(20)	58-59°	230-31°	175°
	2) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-3-valeryl benzoate (EtOH)	(10)	48-50°	175°	154-55°
<i>n</i> -Caproylchloride	3) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-5-caproyl benzoate (dil. EtOH)	(5)	54-55°	230°	180-81°
	4) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-3-caproyl benzoate (dil. EtOH)	(3)	47-48°	222-23°	138-39°
<i>p</i> -Toluoylchloride	5) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-5-toluoyl benzoate (EtOH)	(17)	148-49°	270-71°	227-28°
	6) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-3-toluoyl benzoate (glacial HAC)	(15)	191-92°	156-57°	220-21°

m.p. of the DNP derivatives of II and III have been reported to be 270° and 283° respectively. We find the m.p.s. are as under: II, 92-93°, III, 86-87°, DNP of II, 195°, DNP of III, 262-64°.

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Limiting Apparent Molal Volume of NaNO_3 and KNO_3 in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at Different Temperatures.

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THE variation of the limiting apparent molal volume (ϕ°) of electrolytes with temperatures have been employed to study ion solvent interaction by many workers both in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions, since it is the simplest thermodynamic property to measure¹⁻⁵. The variation of ' ϕ° ' with nonaqueous solvents is generally expressed on the basis of the weakening of the ion-dipole interaction energy. To have a more general idea about the behaviour of salts in nonaqueous solvents, the apparent molal volume ' ϕ° ' of NaNO_3 and KNO_3 in 10,20 and 30% dioxane-water mixtures at 30,35,40 and 45° have been calculated from the density data in the usual manner. The dioxane-water mixtures have been employed because of varying dielectric constants with a little tendency of hydrogen bonding.

In this present note, an attempt has been made to deal with the nature of the ion-solvent interaction of the salts in mixed solvents to see the effect of the dielectric constant, temperature and electrostriction on limiting apparent molal volume.

NaNO_3 and KNO_3 used were E. P. 'E. Merck' variety. The preparation of solvents, solutions and the measurements were the same as described by Prasad and coworkers⁶.

TABLE I— ϕ° VALUES

Salts	Temperature (°C)	10%D	20%D	30%D
NaNO_3	30	24.50	25.80	28.90
	35	27.24	29.81	31.33
	40	32.48	34.42	35.21
	45	36.31	38.80	40.41
KNO_3	30	30.74	32.48	35.91
	35	35.71	37.48	40.91
	40	40.58	41.45	45.48
	45	41.80	43.42	48.10

The ' ϕ° ' values for NaNO_3 and KNO_3 at 10,20 and 30% dioxane content and at different temperatures, evaluated in the usual manner³ are given in table I. The ' ϕ° ' values were found to be linear with temperature. The $d\phi^\circ/dt$ increases sharply with the increase in dioxane content in case of NaNO_3 but it is small in case of KNO_3 . This indicates that ion-solvent interaction is somewhat stronger in case of NaNO_3 and less in case of KNO_3 . This difference may be due to the release of solvent molecules loosely bonded to the K^+ ion and of the solvent molecules which may be accommodated inside the larger K^+ and are held by their weak vanderwaals forces.

Dioxane is more or less a nonhydrogen bonded solvent. So the ion-dipole interaction energy in absence of any hydrogen bond energy, would be appreciable and the attachment of the solvent molecules even to Na^+ and K^+ may not be loose; at the same time no structure formation would occur in the solvent around the ions⁷, as the dioxane content in the medium increases. The net result will be greater solvation. Now some solvent molecules will be associated with ions, while outside the ion-sphere, the solvent structure would almost be the same as that of the pure solvent and hence the expansion of the solution on heating would be comparatively less than that of the pure solvent and hence $d\phi^\circ/dt$ in case of NaNO_3 is sharp with increase in dioxane content. The attachment of solvent molecules is less in case of K^+ and hence $d\phi^\circ/dt$ does not change appreciably. Thus the variation of ' ϕ° ' with temperature appears to be satisfactorily explained by the concept of ion-solvent interaction and solvation.

It would be interesting to consider the electrostriction i.e. contraction of the solvent molecules in presence of electrolytes by comparing the limiting apparent molal volume of different dielectric constant. An increasing trend of ' ϕ° ' values with decrease in dielectric constant is very much noticeable. High dielectric constant would lower the electrostatic attraction of the ions on the solvent molecules resulting in a smaller contraction of the solvent. Hence in the present case, increasing trend of ' ϕ° ' with decrease in dielectric constant, suggests some contraction in the solvents.

Another interesting fact to which attention may now be drawn is that in the difference in ' ϕ° ' values of NaNO_3 - KNO_3 in solvents considered for the present communication is around 5-8 ml/mole and is almost independent of temperature. This difference i.e. 5-8 ml/mole does not correspond to the difference in the intrinsic volume of the ions obtained from the relation $4/3\pi r^3 N$, where 'r' being the radius of the ion in question as given by Robinson and Stokes⁸. This difference arises due to electrostriction or contraction in the solvents.

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